

Estimation of the variance V in (A2.1)

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The variance V in eq. (A2.1) couples the mean error of a measurement of the distance between two stars in the grid system to the "mean error per orbit" of a star's position along the reference great circle. In Høg's note 11 it was estimated by an analogy to the determination of division corrections. For a density $\varrho = 1 \text{ star deg}^{-2}$ and field width $w = 1^\circ$ we get $V = 0.50$ ($m = 3$) or $V = 0.30$ ($m = 4$). $m-1$ is the average number of stars to which a particular star is tied by direct measurements of distances in the grid system (each measurement being counted once only, i.e. from star 1 to star 2 but not from star 2 to star 1). m depends on the length of the field of view.

The main objection to this method is that the actual (random) distribution of stars in both coordinates is not taken into account. Furthermore, the pole of the scan moves continuously during observations and in order to determine all instrumental constants we have to consider more than one orbit at a time.

More precise estimates of V have been obtained from numerical experiments carried out as follows. The parameters determining the problem are:

- ϱ = density of stars (deg^{-2})
- w, l = width and length of either field of view (deg)
- γ = basic angle (deg)
- n_0 = number of consecutive orbits considered in one solution
- ω = speed at which the axis of rotation changes direction
(deg/orbit)

The procedure is straight-forward. Random stellar positions with the given average density are generated and "scanned" by the two fields. Every possible connexion (two stars in the complex field at the same time) is recorded and the equation of condition (A1.1, page 4) is formulated. However, the left member (the O-C) is replaced by a random gaussian number with unit variance. All p-f connexions were recorded in this way but in the frequent case when two stars might be connected both p-p and f-f, only one of them (chosen at random) was recorded. After all "observations" have been made, a check is made that every star is (directly or indirectly) connected to all other stars, and that the chain of connexions make up a closed circle.

The normal equations are formed and the equation $\sum_i dv_i = 0$ and the corresponding Lagrangean multiplier added. The equations are solved according to the method of conjugate gradients (see below). The unknowns which are determined are dv_i for each star, and six instrumental constants (basic angle correction, scale value, zero-point perpendicular to the scan, and three angles for the orientation and tilt of the grid). We then have

$$V = p \cdot \langle dv_i^2 \rangle$$

where p is the average number of orbits in this group during which a star is observed:

$$p = (N, \text{ total number of stars in the group}) / (360^\circ \cdot w \cdot \varphi).$$

Table 1 shows some results of the experiments. n_c is the number of connexions or angle measurements, $t = 0.8 \cdot 95^m n_o / n_c$ is the average time available for each angle measurement. $(V/t)^{0.5}$ is the mean error of dv_i in terms of the mean error of an angle measurement obtained with 1^s integration time.

Table 1. Result of numerical simulations of step 1.

Constant parameters: $\varphi = 1 \text{ star deg}^{-2}$, $n_o = 8$, $\omega = 0.28 \text{ /orbit}$.

γ	w	l	N	n_c	$\langle dv_i^2 \rangle$	p	V	t	$(V/t)^{0.5}$
60°	0.9°	1.2°	765	7904	0.285	2.36	0.672	4.62	0.38
63	0.9	1.2	765	7834	0.0829	2.36	0.196	4.66	0.205
64	0.9	1.2	765	7879	0.0813	2.36	0.192	4.63	0.204
63	0.9	1.4	765	9097	0.0690	2.36	0.163	4.01	0.202

- Conclusions:
1. $\gamma = 60^\circ$ is unfavourable, as predicted by the simplified analysis (Høg's note 11)
 2. A longer field decreases V but this is compensated by the shorter time available for each connexion.
 3. $V = 0.20$ rather than 0.5 used in the MDS.

Remark on the solution of the system of normal equations

A remarkable feature of the method of conjugate gradients is that the solution is made recursively (monotonically decreasing quadratic form) reminding of other iterative methods, but is finite, i.e. if no round-off errors are present the exact solution is obtained after n recursions, n being the number of unknowns. The method is efficient only if the recursion is terminated after much less than n steps. In our case $n = 772$. After each recursion, the mean square residual and the mean square solution $\langle dv_i^2 \rangle$ were computed. It turned out that about 100 recursions are sufficient to give $\langle dv_i^2 \rangle$ to within 10^{-3} ; at this stage the mean square residual was about 10^{-8} times the value at the beginning. Convergence to full numeric accuracy (8 digits), or mean square residual 10^{-16} , required about 300 recursions. The rapid convergence indicates that the system is very well conditioned. The figures quoted above are for $\phi = 63^\circ$ and 64° . For $\phi = 60^\circ$, about 200 recursions were required to obtain full accuracy!

The programme was written in Fortran and run on Univac 1100. It requires about 60 k words and typically 10^2 CPU time for one experiment (300 recursions).

* see, e.g., J.K. Reid (ed.), Large Sparse Sets of Linear Equations, p. 231, Academic Press London & New York 1971, and H.R. Schwarz, Numerik Symmetrischer Matrizen, B.G. Teubner, Stuttgart 1972.

log r (relative residual of normal equations)

X rms

.3

.2

.1

0

0

50

100

150

200

250

300

MOORE INSTRUMENT
SERIAL NUMBER
CREATED IN THE U.S.A.

GRAPHIC